

Original Research

Mass of amalgam restorations and its significance for assessing the environmental impact of dental amalgam

Iztok Štampfelj^{1,2,*}, Neža Gozdnikar^{3†}, Nika Junež^{3†}, Anja Konjar^{3†}, Lorena Lina Perpar^{3†}, Eva Polšak^{3†}

Abstract

Although many countries are phasing out dental amalgam use, numerous amalgam restorations will remain in the mouths of people. Reliable estimates of the mass of amalgam restorations are severely lacking, making it difficult to assess the contribution of dental amalgam to environmental pollution with mercury. In this study, the mass of 245 amalgam restorations was measured after mechanical removal from permanent teeth extracted in Slovenia. The differences in restoration mass according to the tooth type (premolars, upper molars, lower molars) and the number of amalgam-restored surfaces (1, 2, \geq 3) were assessed by using a two-way analysis of variance. Predictions were made using a multiple linear regression model. The mass of restorations ranged from 0.03 to 3.00 g with a mean value of 0.71 g. The number of restored surfaces was a more important explanatory variable (effect size 0.54, 95% CI 0.48–0.61) than the tooth type (effect size 0.25, 95% CI 0.17–0.33). A multiple linear regression model explained 61% of the variation in restoration mass. This study provides mass estimates for amalgam restorations based on the analysis of a Slovenian sample and supports their association with the number of restored surfaces and tooth type.

Keywords

dental amalgam, mercury, permanent teeth, air pollution.

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Masa amalgamskih restavracij in njen pomen za ovrednotenje okoljskega vpliva dentalnega amalgama

Izvleček

Kljub postopnemu opuščanju uporabe dentalnega amalgama v mnogih državah bodo v ustih ljudi ostale številne amalgamske restavracije. Zanesljivih ocen mase amalgamskih restavracij je zelo malo, kar otežuje določitev prispevka dentalnega amalgama k onesnaženju okolja z živim srebrom. V tej raziskavi je bila izmerjena masa 245 amalgamskih restavracij, ki so bile predhodno mehansko odstranjene iz stalnih zob, ekstrahiranih v Sloveniji. Razlike med masami restavracij glede na vrsto zoba (ličniki, zgornji kočniki in spodnji kočniki) in število amalgamsko obnovljenih zobnih ploskev (1, 2 in ≥ 3) so bile ovrednotene z dvosmerno analizo variance. Za izračun napovedi je bil uporabljen model multiple linearne regresije. Masa amalgamskih restavracij je bila od 0.03 do 3.00 g, njena povprečna vrednost pa 0.71 g. Število obnovljenih zobnih ploskev je bilo pomembnejša pojasnjevalna spremenljivka (velikost učinka = 0,54, 95 % IZ 0,48–0,61) kakor vrsta zoba (velikost učinka = 0,25, 95 % IZ 0,17–0,33). Model multiple linearne regresije je pojasnil 61 % variabilnosti mase restavracij. Raziskava prispeva ocene mase amalgamskih restavracij na podlagi analize slovenskega vzorca in potrjuje njihovo povezanost s številom obnovljenih zobnih ploskev in vrsto zoba.

Ključne besede

dentalni amalgam, živo srebro, stalni zobje, onesnaženje zraka.

Introduction

Mercury is a toxic heavy metal and, according to the World Health Organisation (WHO), one of the top 10 chemicals of major public health concern (WHO, 2024). The main target organs for mercury toxicity in humans are the brain, liver, and kidneys; fetuses and small children are particularly vulnerable because mercury adversely affects their development (Clarkson, 1997). Mercury occurs in three forms, which are all toxic: elemental (or metallic), inorganic, and organic (e.g., methylmercury, which is the most toxic). Elemental mercury is released into the environment as a result of natural processes, including geothermal activity and volcanism, but the largest emissions are related to human activities, including burning of fossil fuels (which contain mercury as a trace contaminant), generation of mercury-containing wastes, mercury use in industrial processes, in products, in dental applications, and in mining for mercury and for other minerals (Pacyna et al., 2010). Elemental mercury ultimately enters the aquatic ecosystems, where it is converted to methylmercury by microorganisms, and then bioaccumulates and biomagnifies as it ascends the aquatic food chain. Human exposure mainly occurs through consumption of fish and other seafood contaminated with

methylmercury and occupationally related inhalation of elemental mercury vapours (WHO, 2024).

Contemporary dental amalgam is a mixture of mercury with an alloy that is composed mostly of silver, tin, and copper (Powers & Wataha, 2017). Dental amalgam has been used extensively for almost 200 years because of its versatility as a direct-placement dental restorative material, excellent mechanical properties, ease of manipulation, clinical longevity of restorations, and low cost. Its disadvantages are inferior aesthetic appearance (due to colour mismatch with the tooth) and absence of adhesion to tooth structure. From the very beginning, there have been speculations suggesting a link between health problems and amalgam restorations (Hyson, 2006); however, in the set amalgam mercury is bound with stable metallic bonds and its absorption by the body, while detectable, does not approach the levels known to cause adverse health effects (Berglund, 1990; Bajsman et al., 2014). No other restorative material has been as thoroughly toxicologically evaluated as dental amalgam (Frankenberger et al., 2021). Notably, several scientific committees and professional organisations, including the Scientific Committee on Emerging and Newly Identified Health Risks (SCENIHR) and the International Association for Dental Research (IADR), have affirmed the safety of

dental amalgam, except for patients with allergies to amalgam components or severe renal diseases (Pezelj-Ribarić et al., 2008; Rodríguez-Farre et al., 2016; Ajiboye et al., 2020).

Of greater concern are environmental risks and indirect health effects associated with releases of mercury from dental amalgam into the environment as a result of inappropriate amalgam waste management in dental practices and pollution from crematoriums due to vaporisation of amalgam restorations in the teeth of corpses during cremation. According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the dental amalgam in 2010 contributed 21–32% and 9–13% to overall EU mercury emissions to the air and surface water, respectively (Ajiboye et al., 2020). Although many countries are phasing out dental amalgam use, the related environmental issues will remain relevant for decades to come due to the amount of existing amalgam restorations in the mouths of living people. In developed countries, the legislation requires the use of highly efficient amalgam-particle separators and ensures a regulated collection system for mercury-contaminated solid waste to minimise leakages from dental clinics to the environment. In contrast, no specific legislation applies to toxic emissions from crematoriums at the EU level, and the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has provided no specific recommendations for these facilities (Mari & Domingo, 2010). Moreover, crematorium emissions have not been the subject of the Minamata Con-

vention on Mercury, signed in 2013, which aims to reduce global mercury pollution (UNEP, 2024).

From a public health point of view, it is therefore important to accurately estimate the total potential contribution of crematoriums to the annual atmospheric flux of anthropogenic mercury. However, the lack of reliable data on the mass of amalgam restorations limits our ability to model these estimates using national oral health data, and rates of mortality and corpse cremation (Santarsiero et al., 2006; Piagno & Afshari, 2020). Additionally, the mass of mercury in the cremated body (Hg input), which is inferred from the mass of amalgam restorations, is an important variable in the assessment of the effectiveness of various abatement techniques available for reducing mercury emissions from crematoriums (Ohle et al., 2021).

Only one study from Canada has so far used a large sample of amalgam restorations (from both natural and anatomical replica teeth) and developed multiple regression models to predict their mass (Adegbelembo et al., 2004). Additionally, two US studies reported mean masses for samples of only 10 and 40 amalgam restorations (Reinhardt et al., 1983; Drummond et al., 2003). The aim of the present study was to estimate the mass of amalgam restorations in a Slovenian population; the predictors included in the model were the number of restored surfaces and the type of tooth (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of amalgam restorations (from left to right): (1) one-surface restoration on a lower first premolar, (2) two-surface restoration on an upper first premolar, (3) three-surface restoration on an upper first molar, (4) four-surface restoration on a lower first molar. Tooth surfaces: m. – mesial, d. – distal, b. – buccal, li. – lingual. Dotted lines indicate the boundaries between amalgam-restored tooth surfaces. Adapted from the first Slovenian textbook of dental anatomy (Logar, 1955).

Slika 1. Shematski prikaz amalgamskih restavracij (od leve proti desni): (1) enoploskovna restavracija na spodnjem prvem ličniku, (2) dvoploskovna restavracija na zgornjem prvem ličniku, (3) triploskovna restavracija na zgornjem prvem kočniku, (4) štiriploskovna restavracija na spodnjem prvem kočniku. Zobne ploskve: m. – mezialna, d. – distalna, b. – bukalna, li. – lingvalna. Pikčaste črte označujejo meje med amalgamsko obnovljenimi zobnimi ploskvami. Prirejeno po prvem slovenskem učbeniku anatomije zob (Logar, 1955).

Materials and Methods

Amalgam-restored permanent teeth

This study was approved by the Slovenian National Medical Ethics Committee (Approval No. 0120-160/2025-2711-3). The permanent teeth containing amalgam restorations were taken from a dental collection at the Faculty of Medicine in Ljubljana (Department of Dental Diseases and Dental Morphology). This collection is a repository of de-identified teeth approved for use in teaching and research. The restorations have been placed by dentists practising in Slovenia, but the time of placement was unknown.

Removal and weighing of amalgam restorations

The amalgam restorations were removed from their cavities by crushing the teeth between two metal hammers inside a transparent plastic bag to avoid losing any fractured pieces of amalgam. Under the Motic stereomicroscope (Model SMZ-161-TP, Hong Kong, China), each removed amalgam restoration was inspected, and any remnants of the underlying base material were removed using hand cures and petite round burs with a long neck (EndoTracer, Komet Dental, Lemgo, Germany) in a Synea WA-86-LT slow-speed handpiece (W&H Dentalwerk, Bürmoos, Austria). The contents of the plastic bag were placed on a sheet of white paper and scrutinised under the stereomicroscope for the presence of amalgam particles. Each amalgam restoration was weighed using an EW600-2M scale (Kern & Sohn, Balingen, Germany) to a precision of 0.01 g. In accordance with the Slovenian legislation (Government of the Republic of Slovenia, 2008), all amalgam restorations were stored under water in tightly capped containers before they were taken over by an authorised amalgam waste recycler.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were reported as means and standard deviation (SD). Normality of the data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. The differences in restoration mass according to tooth type (premolars, upper molars, and lower molars) and number of restored surfaces (1, 2, and ≥ 3) were tested by using a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). *P*-values were adjusted for multiple comparisons using the Holm method (Holm, 1979). A multi-

ple linear regression model was used to predict restoration mass, with results presented as 95% confidence intervals. *P*-values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed in R 4.0.0 (R Core Team, 2025).

Results

In this study, 245 amalgam restorations were removed from 226 permanent teeth (78 premolars, 86 upper molars, and 62 lower molars). Figure 2 shows examples of removed amalgam restorations. The mass of amalgam restorations ranged from 0.03 to 3.00 g (both limits recorded in lower molars) with a mean value of 0.71 g (SD 0.60 g) (Table 1). The total weight of amalgam removed from 522 restored tooth surfaces was 173.41 g or 0.33 g per restored surface removed. In all tooth types, the mean mass of the restorations increased with the number of restored surfaces (Fig. 3). The mean mass of restorations was similar for upper and lower molars, regardless of the number of restored surfaces, while it was lower for premolars (Fig. 3).

The effects of the individual factors on the mass of the amalgam restorations and the interaction between them were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$ for both the tooth type and number of restored surfaces; $p = 0.014$ for the interaction). The result of the *post-hoc* analysis is shown in Fig. 4. For one restored surface, all three pairwise comparisons showed no significant differences between tooth types. In contrast, the upper molar vs. premolar and lower molar vs. premolar comparisons showed significant differences for two restored surfaces ($p < 0.001$) and for ≥ 3 restored surfaces ($p < 0.001$).

The linear regression model with the number of restored surfaces and tooth type as predictors explained 61% of the variation in the masses of restorations, hence failing to account for 39% of this variation. Considering the effect of each factor, the number of restored surfaces explained more variation (effect size = 0.54, 95% CI 0.48–0.61) than the tooth type (effect size = 0.25, 95% CI 0.17–0.33) and the between-factor interaction (effect size = 0.05, 95% CI 0.01–0.10). The predicted mean mass was highest with ≥ 3 restored surfaces and lowest with one restored surface, regardless of the type of tooth, but when comparing tooth types, premolars had the lowest predicted mass of amalgam restorations for all numbers of restored surfaces (Fig. 5).

Figure 2. Amalgam restorations removed from permanent teeth (from left to right): (1) one-surface restoration from an upper molar, (2) two-surface restoration from an upper premolar, (3) three-surface restoration from a lower molar, (4) four-surface restoration from an upper molar, and (5) five-surface restoration from an upper molar.

Slika 2. Amalgamske restavracije, odstranjene iz stalnih zob (od leve proti desni): (1) enoploskovna restavracija iz zgornjega kočnika, (2) dvoploskovna restavracija iz zgornjega ličnika, (3) triploskovna restavracija iz spodnjega kočnika, (4) štiriploskovna restavracija iz zgornjega kočnika in (5) petploskovna restavracija iz zgornjega kočnika.

Tabela 1. Summary of the masses of amalgam restorations (g).

Table 1. Masa amalgamskih restavracij (g)

No. of restored surfaces	Upper molar				Lower molar				Premolar				All			
	n	Mean	SD	95% CI	n	Mean	SD	95% CI	n	Mean	SD	95% CI	n	Mean	SD	95% CI
1	26	0.32	0.22	0.23–0.41	26	0.29	0.19	0.22–0.37	25	0.10	0.04	0.09–0.12	77	0.24	0.19	0.20–0.28
2	24	0.87	0.40	0.7–1.04	21	0.84	0.47	0.63–1.05	41	0.37	0.20	0.30–0.43	86	0.62	0.42	0.53–0.71
≥3	40	1.40	0.56	1.22–1.58	21	1.43	0.65	1.13–1.72	21	0.74	0.30	0.60–0.87	82	1.24	0.60	1.11–1.37
All	90	0.95	0.63	0.81–1.08	68	0.81	0.65	0.65–0.97	87	0.38	0.30	0.31–0.44	245	0.71	0.60	0.63–0.78

n – number of restorations, SD – standard deviation, CI – confidence interval.

n – število restavracij, SD – standardni odklon, CI – interval zaupanja.

Figure 3. Mean mass of amalgam restorations with 95% confidence interval, according to tooth type and number of restored surfaces.

Slika 3. Povprečna masa amalgamskih restavracij s 95 % intervalom zaupanja glede na vrsto zoba in število amalgamsko obnovljenih ploskev.

Figure 4. Forest plot of the mean differences in mass of the amalgam restorations between the tooth types, according to the number of restored surfaces. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05, CI – confidence interval, UM – upper molar, LM – lower molar, P – premolar.

Slika 4. Gozdni diagram povprečnih razlik v masi amalgamskih restavracij med vrstami zob glede na število amalgamsko obnovljenih ploskev. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05, CI – interval zaupanja, UM – zgornji kočnik, LM – spodnji kočnik, P – ličnik.

Figure 5. Predicted mean mass of amalgam restorations (and 95% confidence intervals), according to the tooth type and number of restored surfaces.

Slika 5. Napovedana povprečna masa amalgamskih restavracij (in 95-odstotni intervali zaupanja) glede na vrsto zoba in število amalgamsko obnovljenih ploskev.

Discussion

In the present study, there was a 100-fold difference between the mass of the lightest and heaviest amalgam restoration (0.03 and 3.00 g, respectively), which greatly exceeds the ranges reported by Takaoka et al. (2010) for Japanese (0.056–0.231 g) and dental materials manufacturer Vivadent (0.2–1.8 g) (Sobolewski, 2016); however, the size of the samples was not specified in these reports. Considering that dental amalgam contains approximately 50% of mercury by mass, our results indicate that during corpse cremation, from 0.015 to 1.5 g of mercury may be released from one amalgam restoration, corresponding to the disposal of 4 to 375 fluorescent bulbs; these, on average, contain 0.004 g of mercury (Mulligan et al., 2018).

Only data from the study by Adegbenbo et al. (2004) are available for a more detailed comparison with the results of the present study, but the methodological differences between them must first be evaluated. Firstly, our study sample consisted of restorations placed in natural teeth by Slovenian dentists, whereas the comparative sample consisted of restorations placed in both natural and anatomical replica teeth by Canadian dentists and dental students, respectively. Secondly, in our study, the amalgam restorations were isolated by crushing the teeth, weighed, and then stored for recycling, whereas the authors of the comparative research took an indirect approach of subtracting the tooth masses recorded before and after drilling away the amalgam restoration from the cavity. In this respect, the indirect method is non-destructive and leaves the extracted teeth usable (e.g., for pre-clinical teaching or training); however, it has potential shortcomings, including a time-consuming and laborious process of drilling away the amalgam from numerous teeth, which is neither friendly to the environment nor the health of researchers. Thirdly, in comparison with the previous research, the cut-off value for the number of surfaces restored with amalgam was reduced from ≥ 4 to ≥ 3 because there was a very small number of restorations with ≥ 4 restored surfaces in the premolar and lower molar groups (3 and 6, respectively), in spite of the greater total sample size (245 vs. 155 restorations from the natural teeth). Thus, setting the cut-off value at ≥ 4 would yield imprecise statistical estimates, consequently hindering our ability to draw valid inferences based on such a small group size.

Some findings of the present study are in agreement with those reported in the previous investigation: The

mean restoration mass and SD ($0.71 \text{ g} \pm 0.60 \text{ g}$) are comparable with values obtained for amalgam-restored teeth extracted from Canadian patients at the time of the study ($0.67 \text{ g} \pm 0.43 \text{ g}$) or at least 15 years earlier ($0.60 \text{ g} \pm 0.46 \text{ g}$). The mean mass of the restorations within each tooth type increased as the number of tooth surfaces restored with amalgam increased. Moreover, the restorations with two or \geq three restored surfaces were significantly heavier in upper and lower molars than in premolars, paralleling the trends observed in the Canadian investigation. This has been explained by the smaller crown size in premolars than molars, the former facilitating placement of smaller restorations (Adegbenbo et al., 2004). However, another factor that may be taken into consideration is a characteristic pattern of dental destruction caused by caries: molars are more commonly affected than premolars and enter into the repeat restoration cycle earlier, which over time results in heavier restorations (Pitts et al., 2003; Schwendicke et al., 2018). Our linear regression model using the tooth type and number of restored surfaces to assess the variation of restoration masses explained 61% of this variation. This is comparable to the Canadian model, in which the same variables explained 54% of the variation observed in natural teeth. Additionally, in both studies, the number of restored surfaces was the most important explanatory variable.

In this study, the mean mass of amalgam per restored surface was 0.33 g. In contrast, Adegbenbo et al. (2002) in another study reported a value almost twice as high (0.65 g), but their sample was very small (38 restored tooth surfaces) and the tooth type was not specified. Moreover, the restorations with ≥ 2 restored surfaces were on average slightly heavier in molars from Slovenia than in those from North America (Drummond et al., 2003; Adegbenbo et al., 2004); the reverse was true for the restorations with one restored surface in molars and for the restorations in premolars, regardless of the number of restored surfaces. The reasons for this pattern are not clear, but apparently, they are neither related to (i) different methods of determining the mass of restorations nor to (ii) variable trends in dental caries prevalence and severity in the source populations.

Regarding the first, the indirect approach used in a study by Adegbenbo et al. (2004) could produce slightly overestimated restoration masses, because removal of amalgam using burs invariably results in cavity enlargement (Hunter et al., 1995; Dörter et al., 2003; Sardenberg et al., 2008; Lenzi et al., 2013). However, contrary to the expectation, the extensive restorations in molars (≥ 2 restored surfaces)

were, on average, lighter than in our study, in spite of the fact that such restorations are, in general, less regularly shaped and thus more difficult to drill away from the cavity without sacrificing tooth structure. Regarding the second, Adegbebo et al. (2004) found no significant differences between mean masses of restorations from extracted teeth collected at the time of study and at least 15 years previously, in spite of a significant reduction in the prevalence of cavitated caries lesions and the decayed, missing, and filled (DMF) index scores over decades in North America (Frencken et al., 2017). The restoration mass is dependent upon several factors, including the extent of the carious lesion at the time of diagnosis and the number of restoration cycles, i.e., replacements due to secondary caries lesions or other causes of amalgam failure, perhaps indicating a later diagnosis and/or a higher number of replacements in molars from Slovenia than in those from North America. The exact cause for the observed pattern of differences between studies is difficult to ascertain because in both, the restorations were taken from a non-random pool of extracted teeth. Besides, the concept of extension for prevention, which the profession has followed for decades (Vrbič, 1981), should also be considered as one of the factors increasing the restoration mass. According to this concept, not only was the lesion included in the cavity outline, but also the neighbouring caries-prone areas, such as non-carious grooves on occlusal surfaces. In Slovenia, this concept was abandoned in favour of the more conservative cavity designs in 1990 (Vrbič, 1990).

Estimating mercury emissions from crematoriums requires calculation of the emissions factor, which is the mean mass of mercury (in grams) contained in the amalgam restorations of deceased individuals (Santarsiero et al., 2006). The emissions factor for mercury release from crematoriums is population-specific due to variations in dental amalgam use and mortality rates among countries. For the UK, a high factor value of 3.0 g was derived in 1990 by weighing the amount of mercury in one medium-sized amalgam capsule (0.6 g) and estimating that adult individuals on average carry five amalgam restorations (Mills, 1990). In Switzerland, around the same time, an average mercury content of 2.1 g per corpse was found on the basis of postmortem clinical and radiographical examinations and unpublished data on the mass of variously sized amalgam restorations (Matter-Grütter et al., 1995). Recently, a British Columbia-specific emissions factor of 1.2 g was developed based on mortality data, mean number of amalgam-restored

tooth surfaces per person, by age category, and mean mass of 1-surface amalgam restoration (0.26 g) from the study of Adegbebo et al. (2004), assuming this value as a contribution of each restored tooth surface to the total mass of amalgam (Piagno & Afshari, 2020). In contrast, much lower values of 0.078 g and 0.060 g were recently reported for Germany, based on the environmental modelling and emissions testing conducted in 26 crematoriums, respectively (Sobolewski, 2016). The environmental modelling employed the postmortem examination-based mean number of 0.39 amalgam restorations per cremated body and the mean mass of 0.2 g of mercury per restoration, as reported by the dental materials manufacturer. A comparably low value of 0.032 g was recently obtained for Japan by monitoring mercury emission from 7 crematoriums (Takaoka et al., 2010).

As apparent from the above, the mass of amalgam restorations was not determined empirically, but rather estimated based on simplified or unpublished data, thus forming the least reliable variable in modelling mercury emissions. The present study goes some way towards overcoming this limitation. In future assessments, the predicted masses of amalgam restorations in conjunction with analysis of the oral health records of representative population samples will enable refinement of mercury emission estimates from this source of pollution, specifically, the calculation should account for both the number of tooth surfaces restored with amalgam and tooth type and provide the lower and upper values of the emissions factor.

In the EU, dentistry was identified as the largest remaining consumer of mercury, which encouraged the decision-makers to take legislative actions targeting the use of dental amalgam and the amalgam waste management (European Commission, 2020). Consequently, the use and export of dental amalgam is prohibited since 1 January 2025; however, for Member States requiring more time to adapt their national healthcare systems, including Slovenia, the ban will come into effect by 30 June 2026 (European Commission, 2024). Although patient doubts about dental amalgam safety remain, it must be emphasised that the reason for its abandonment is not medical concerns but environmental issues and indirect health effects associated with releases of mercury into the environment. Crematoriums are currently an unregulated source of harmful air pollutants, including mercury from amalgam restorations, which is a concerning issue in light of the worldwide increasing cremation rates (Mari & Domingo, 2010; Tibau & Grube, 2019). Although the contribution of crematoriums

to mercury pollution is small in comparison with some other sources, like coal-fired power plants and municipal waste incinerators, their predominant location in or close to residential areas and comparatively low chimneys might result in a completely different emission situation in the vicinity of these facilities (Ohle et al., 2021). Nevertheless, only a few studies have been published on emissions from crematoriums, mostly focusing on dioxins, volatile organic compounds, and particulate matter (Hutzinger & Fiedler, 1993; Takeda et al., 2000; Takeda et al., 2001; Luthardt et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2003; Xue et al., 2018).

Limitations

The primary limitation of his study is that the sampling type was convenience, not probabilistic. Additionally, the time of restoration placement and the age and biological sex of the patients were not known. These limitations are common if the extracted teeth from existing dental collections are used as a study material. The primary strength of the study is a direct method of determining the mass of amalgam restorations, which surpasses the previously used indirect method in terms of accuracy, safety, and time efficiency.

Conclusions

This study estimated the mass of amalgam restorations based on the analysis of a Slovenian sample, thereby providing data that should enable reliable modelling of

mercury emissions from crematoriums and assessment of their impact on the surrounding environment. The linear regression model with the number of restored surfaces and tooth type as predictors explained 61% of the variation in the masses of restorations. This is only the second study investigating the mass of amalgam restorations, and further research is needed to shed more light on its temporal and global variation.

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation, I.Š.; Supervision, I.Š.; Funding acquisition, I.Š.; Development of methodology, I.Š.; Writing the initial draft, I.Š.; Investigation, N.J., N.G., L.L.P., E.P., and A.K.; Writing – review & editing, N.J., N.G., L.L.P., E.P., and A.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

Research data is deposited at Zenodo (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17954485>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

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